

Note on Some Derivatives of Diphenylmethane.

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During the last few years much attention has been given to the problem of the position in space of the phenyl groups in diphenyl, and a survey of the position has recently been made in the *Annual Report of the Chemical Society* (1926, p. 119-125).

The author has made numerous experiments with the object of preparing the hydrocarbon (I) but the results have not been published owing to the appearance of an almost identical piece of work by Sircar and De (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 245). In both cases negative results were obtained. In continuation, the investigation was extended to derivatives of diphenylmethane, which both Kaufler (*Annalen*, 1907, 381, 151 ; *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 3250) and Montague and Van Charante (*Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1912, 31, 848) had suggested might possess a folded structure similar to the one proposed by Kaufler for diphenyl.

While this work was in progress, it was shown by Butler and Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 2610) that the deductions of Montague and Van Charante were incorrect and this rendered it unlikely that it would be possible to join the rings in diphenylmethane by a second linkage (III). It seemed advisable, however, to record the results. For this purpose the removal of hydrogen bromide from the bromo derivative of 4-methyldiphenylmethane (II) or the elimination of iodine from 4:4'-di-iododiphenylmethane (IV) seemed to offer the greatest prospect of success.

The former of these two reactions was not investigated but a large number of experiments were carried out with the di-iodo deri-

commenced to separate and the reaction mixture ultimately became a thick paste. After the addition of ice the solid was collected and recrystallised from amyl alcohol (yield 60 per cent.). The same product was obtained when the bromo derivative was added to fuming nitric acid at 0°.

4:4'-Dibromo-3:3'-dinitrodiphenylmethane crystallised from amyl alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 238-240°. It was sparingly soluble in ordinary organic solvents. (Found: N, 7.0; Br, 38.4. $C_{14}H_8O_2N_2Br_2$ requires N, 6.7; Br, 38.5 per cent.).

4:4'-Dibromo-3:3'-dinitrobenzophenone.—4:4'-Dibromo-3:3'-dinitrodiphenylmethane (2.5 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid and the hot solution gradually treated with chromic acid (2.5 g.) dissolved in acetic acid. When the oxidation was complete, water was added and the ketone collected. It was purified by crystallisation from benzene and melted, as stated by Montague (*loc. cit.*), at 157-158°. (Found: N, 6.8. Calc. N, 6.5 per cent.).

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